

Pigments in 5 plant parts of lowland rices in 9 districts of Uttar Pradesh, India. 1986.

Cultivar	Pigment				
	N	I	L	G	K
<i>Azamgarh</i>					
Bhainsalote	2	9	11	13	25
Derai	9	3	8	14	25
Lakara	1	9	11	13	25
Ramkajara	1	9	11	13	16
Rath	4	2	7	14	16
Selhi	3	9	8	13	16
Sorhi	3	9	8	13	24
T100	6	4	11	13	23
<i>Ballia</i>					
Karinga	7	9	8	14	21
Karingi	3	4	8	18	25
<i>Bahraich</i>					
Madhukar	5	10	11	27	16
<i>Barabanki</i>					
Gajraj	3	4	8	27	24
<i>Basti</i>					
Anandi	1	4	8	32	31
Bansfool	3	4	8	16	19
Bansfore	5	4	11	14	19
Brahma	20	9	8	16	18
Duniapat	5	9	11	13	23
Foolbagan	9	9	7	14	1
Gauria A	1	9	8	13	20
Gauria B	2	9	11	18	1
Kanakjiri	2	9	11	32	21
Motibadam	1	9	8	13	20
Sengar A	2	1	8	26	1
Sengar B	2	9	8	28	16
Sugpankhi A	5	4	8	14	25
Sugpankhi B	7	9	8	18	25
Sonachur	4	1	11	13	25
T9	2	9	8	13	1
<i>Gonda</i>					
Tulsifool	9	9	7	29	19
<i>Mirzapur</i>					
Bhedkabra	9	5	7	27	1
Dato	2	9	8	14	21
Deharadoon	2	9	8	13	22
Jilhore	4	9	11	14	19
Karanga	1	4	11	26	30
Kesar	3	1	11	13	25
Latera	9	9	11	19	1
Lejura	3	9	8	18	16
Saro	2	9	8	12	21
Silhat	1	9	11	13	17
Shyamjira	1	9	3	15	16
<i>Raibarelli</i>					
Bharafool	1	2	7	33	1
<i>Varanasi</i>					
Adamchini	9	4	8	14	31
Lawangchur	1	1	3	28	1
Sahadeia	9	4	3	26	1

index and metroglyph methods. Index values of range of variability were divided into 4 groups using class intervals (see table). All traits except yield and plant height are represented by

rays on the glyph (ray for the same trait have the same position on each glyph). The performance of a particular cultivar is denoted by its index score (see figure). \mathcal{L}

Index score for different traits of upland rice cultivars.

Character	Range of means	Score 1 Value <	Score 2	Score 3	Score 4 Value >
Days to 50% flowering	57.00- 90.00	67.00	67.00- 78.00	78.10- 89.00	89.00
Internodes (no.)	2.20- 4.80	2.50	2.50- 3.50	3.60- 4.00	4.00
Tillers/plant	5.50- 19.30	8.90	8.90- 12.40	12.50- 15.80	15.80
Panicle length (cm)	18.00- 31.20	21.30	21.30- 24.60	24.70- 28.00	28.00
Grains/panicle	70.00-283.70	123.40	123.40-176.80	176.90-230.30	230.30
Kernel length (mm)	4.25- 6.76	4.88	4.88- 5.51	5.52- 6.15	6.15
Kernel breadth (mm)	1.48- 3.10	1.88	1.88- 2.28	2.29- 2.69	2.69
Test weight (g)	10.89- 31.05	15.93	15.93- 20.97	20.98- 26.02	26.02

Scatter diagram of metroglyph analysis. List of cultivars: 1. Anjani, 2. Ambemohar, 3. ARC-11775, 4. Bagri, 5. Bagri white, 6. Bapri red, 7. Beni, 8. Bakki, 9. Badamfarm, 10. Bendi, 11. Bhadaikakala, 12. Bhattadhan, 13. Browngora, 14. Champa, 15. Chingurdi, 16. Chitrikar, 17. Chali, 18. Chipti, 19. Cauvery, 20. Dehula A, 21. Dehula B, 22. Dhani, 23. Dular, 24. Dudhi A, 25. Dudhi H, 26. Dhudhi C, 27. Dhudhi, 28. Deharadun 2-13-18-17, 29. Gorakhpuri, 30. Gajgaur, 31. Hansraj, 32. Improved Raskadam, 33. Joginia, 34. Jhona 349, 35. Junagarh 68, 36. Kanyadali, 37. Ketki, 38. Kwari, 39. Kalkeri, 40. Karahani A, 41. Karahani B, 42. Kudia, 43. Kachni A, 44. Kachani B, 45. Karangangora, 46. Kolhapur scented, 47. Lurkan, 48. Lalmati A, 49. Lalmati B, 50. Lalnakanda, 51. Mutmuri, 52. Mutmuri A, 53. Maliwa, 54. Nutri A, 55. Mirkirak, 56. Nutan, 57. N22, 58. Nonhigora, 59. Nagpur 14, 60. Nagpur 22, 61. Nagpur 27, 62. Narendra 1, 63. Padhini, 64. Pawas, 65. Panke, 66. Poongar, 67. Raimunia, B, 68. Rengi A, 69. Rengi B, 70. Rengi C, 71. Ranikajal A, 72. Ranikajal B, 73. Ranikajal C, 74. Ranikajal D, 75. Raskadam, 76. Rasi, 77. Surajmukhi, 78. Sawani bagri, 79. Sonkhareha, 80. Sathi, 81. Satha A, 82. Satha B, 83. Satha E, 84. Satha F, 85. Sankhal, 86. Sakurn, 87. Sarya B, 88. Sarya C, 89. Sarya D, 90. Sarya E, 91. Safedwa, 92. Sapna, 93. Thelai, 94. Tinpakhia A, 95. Tinpakhia C, 96. Tinpakhia E, 97. Tecto, and 98. Viagai.

Metroglyph analysis of some upland rice cultivars of India

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Morphological variation of 98 upland rice cultivars was studied using score